

FATIC UNITS IN ESTABLISHING INITIAL CONTACT IN A VIDEO INTERVIEW (ON EXAMPLES FROM RUSSIAN AND BULGARIAN SPEAKERS)

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Abstract

This paper examines the phatic situations in which initial speech contact is initiated in the video interview in Russian and Bulgarian. The frequency of use of the various phatic resources used to establish the first contact with the interlocutor is investigated.

Key words: video interview, phatic communication, phatic emotive, address form.

Phatic speech communication has been a subject of research interest since the mid-twentieth century. In the modern stage of the development of linguistic science, many unexplored issues in the field of phaticism are repeatedly noted. Phatic as a type of communication is a complex multifaceted social process, which provides the fundamental need of man to communicate and lead a normal way of life in the society. The most universal definition of the term phatic communication is related to its social function in society.

In the theoretical basis of phatic communication, different interpretations are observed regarding its nature and functions. There are two main concepts, known in linguistic science as narrow and broad understanding of phatic [5, 11–12].

The so-called narrow understanding relates to ideas of Roman Jakobson, who conceives of phatic communication as a set of ritual polite utterances used by the speaker to establish, maintain, and terminate speech contact [11].

A broader understanding of phatic communication is noted in the works of Malinovsky [1], Aznabaeva [2], Pocheptsov [8], Vinokur [4], Klyuev [7], and others. These researchers qualify phatic as polite non-informative communication that arises in an informal setting, and whose purpose is to create friendly and harmonious relations between communicators.

Such "ordinary friendly conversation" can take place between strangers or people who know each other little, between people who know each other well, and in casual acquaintances [4, 139]. In other words, a person's social need to communicate does not depend on the degree of informativeness in the exchange of messages, but on such factors as etiquette and politeness, which contribute to the creation of harmonious relations and the establishment of an atmosphere of psychological comfort.

Studying the problems of phatic communication and the specifics of speech etiquette in the Russian language, T. G. Vinokur concludes that phatic expressions have a much wider application in everyday human communication.

The term "phatic" is perceived as commencement of dialogue for the purpose of communication: "The general phatic intention is to satisfy the need for communication - cooperative or conflictual, with different forms, tone, relations (degree of closeness) between the

communicants" [4]. The communicative role of the participants in the communication (the way of behaving of the speakers and listeners) is constructed depending on which is leading for the given situation - the information or the contact. The speech behaviour of communicators is based on two different poles - when language is used to receive/send a message and when language is used as an instrument to enter into communication. Thus, informative and phatic forms of communication are organized differently and consist of different target and formal categories of language use [4, 5-6].

G. Vinokur successfully attempts to unite the two understandings into a broader concept, including the conative function (making contact, its maintenance and its verification), the field of speech etiquette, everyday dialogues, artistic dialogues and narratives stylized as everyday [6, 7].

When establishing speech contact, the initial encounter of the speaker with his interlocutor is of utmost importance, which starts the process of forming a friendly/unfriendly relationship. This process is unconditionally based on the communicative interests and goals of the participants in dialogic communication. The speaker, whose intention is to establish communicative contact and create dialogical interaction in the stylistics of cooperative tone, often uses tactics to express politeness to the interlocutor. Establishing a polite tone of communication involves the use of: addressing the interlocutor, greetings, standard speech formulas, paying compliments, expressing positive emotions about the encounter with the interlocutor, inviting the interlocutor to dialogue, etc. In this way, the speaker, choosing his tactics of communication and certain linguistic means, introduces his interlocutor into the dialogue.

In dialogic communication, different stages or phatic situations are marked in which the speaker's intention to establish speech contact with his potential interlocutor is realized. In the study of dialogic units at the initial stage of cooperative or non-cooperative communication, the following phatic situations clearly stand out: identification and attracting the attention of the interlocutor; inviting the interlocutor to participate in the dialogue; making direct speech contact [10, 59].

The video interview as part of dialogic discourse undoubtedly includes all the features of dialogic

speech. But the specificity of this type of communication implies the omission of some of the listed phatic situations. The specificity of the video interview genre shows that identification and attracting the attention of the interlocutor are completely absent as a stage of communicative communication between the interviewer and his interlocutor. The next stage, the interlocutor's invitation to participate in the dialogue, is an important element of communication, but it takes place as a separate ritual act of etiquette that precedes the act of establishing speech contact itself. One of the key aspects of inviting an interlocutor to an interview is the desire to establish a cooperative tone and a congenial atmosphere for future communication in advance. And this is achieved precisely through the basic principles of phatic - showing courtesy and respect to the interlocutor.

It is no coincidence that in the methodological manuals on journalism the specialists advise to maintain a favorable psychological atmosphere through appropriate and contact questions that express not only interest in the interlocutor, but also respect, warmth, responsiveness, acceptance of his views and beliefs, even if they do not coincide with the beliefs and principles of the journalist. During the interview the interlocutor should feel at ease [3].

Greeting

Russian language

Доброе утро! 16 лет не виделись, соскучились невозможно как... (interview by T. Kizyakov with Andrei Derzhavin);

Доброе утро! Так, приветствующих меньше, чем отсутствующих (interview by T. Kizyakov with Valeria and Yosif Prigozhin);

Доброе утро! Пожалуйста, переключку собравшихся (interview by T. Kizyakov with Elena Birukova and Ilya Horoshilov);

Доброе утро! Место, где мы сейчас находимся, что это за место? (interview by T. Kizyakov with Valentina Talzina);

Starting the interview only with a greeting occurs in 19% of the examples studied in the Bulgarian corpus and in 13% of the examples in the Russian corpus. On the other hand, in the Russian interviews an extremely high frequency of use of greeting addresses was found. Address as one of the basic phatic units in dialogic communication plays a central role in situations of establishing speech contact. The pattern of establishing the initial speech contact in the video interview by means of an address with a greeting occurs most frequently in the Russian corpus studied - 48% of the examples contain this pattern.

When studying the stage of establishing speech contact in spontaneous oral communication, the use of various linguistic devices such as greetings, addresses, wishes, compliments, thanks, standard speech formulas, various types of interrogative, inciting and expressive utterances, as well as those directly related to the topic of the conversation are noted.

Similar linguistic devices are used when starting the video interview. Observations show that in forming a favorable beginning and good contact with the interlocutor, the journalist uses greetings, makes a brief positive introduction of his interlocutor, expresses gratitude and interest in him, specifies such parameters of the interview as the purpose, topic, time, which to a considerable extent facilitate a smooth transition to the main topics of discussion.

In the studied corpus of Russian and Bulgarian examples, a different frequency of linguistic means used to establish initial contact is observed. For example, greeting as a universal phatic unit is an important element in human communication, facilitating the creation and maintenance of social ties. It performs various functions related to establishing contact, expressing respect, affirming social norms, and maintaining harmony in society, but its use at the start of the interview in both corpora is highly reduced:

Bulgarian language

Честит рожден ден и честит нов клип! Това ли беше подаръка за празника? (interview by P. Dikova with Simona Zagorova);

Добре дошли! Как сте? -Добре си ме заварила! Честита Нова година (interview by P. Dikova with Nikolina Chakurdukova);

Добре дошли! Как сте днес? -Много благодарим, много сме добре (interview by P. Dikova with Viktoriya Terziyska and her daughters);

Добре дошла! Как си? (interview by P. Dikova with Ivet Lalova);

Добре дошли! Много ми е приятно, че сте тук! Откога не сме се виждали? (interview by P. Dikova with Margarita Hranova and Orlin Goranov);

Добре дошла! Как сте? От колко време сте в България? (interview by P. Dikova with Sashka Vaseva);

Russian Language:

- Доброе утро, Стас, надо проводить переключку, потому что вонь прибывшие появились к великой радости (interview by T. Kiryazov with Stas Mihaylov);

Оксана, доброе утро! 12 лет не виделись на нашей программе, но успехи семейные на лицу (interview by T. Kiryazov with Oksana Fedorovna);

Карен Гарегинович, здравствуйте! Пожалуйста, переключку... (interview by T. Kiryazov with Karen Avanesyan); Жень, доброе утро! Пожалуйста, познакомьте... (interview by T. Kiryazov with Evgeniy Tkachuk);

Доброе утро, товарищи! Азиз, доброе утро! Нужно с пополнением познакомить (interview by T. Kiryazov with Aziza);

Сашь, доброе утро! Пожалуйста, переключку и знакомство с Ольгой (interview by T. Kiryazov with Alik Granovskiy);

Сергей, доброе утро! Пожалуйста, знакомство и переключку (interview by T. Kiryazov with Sergey Penkin);

Варвара, доброе утро! Пожалуйста, познакомьте со своим семейном богатством (interview by T. Kiryazov with the singer Varvara);

Света, доброе утро? У нас уже традиция такая сложилась начинать разговор с чего-то простого, легкого и светлого (interview by T. Kiryazov with Svetlana Horkina);

Ура! Эдуард, доброе утро! У нас в программе всегда интересные люди (interview by T. Kiryazov with Edward Dokunin);

Николай Петрович, доброе утро! Позвольте Вам пожать руку (interview by T. Kiryazov with Nikolai Burlyaev);

Direct initiation of communication

Russian language

Начнем с того, что сегодня происходит сейчас, допустим прям сегодняшней день какие планы на день у Вас (interview by T. Kiryazov with Musalim Magomaev and Tamara Sinyavskaya);

Заслужено присваивается, Андрей, звание народного любимого! Андрей, вот по комплекции можно предположить какой вид спорта, но все-таки лучше от тебя услышать (interview by T. Kiryazov with Andrei Bilanov);

Лади Сергеевич – глава, патриарх сейчас представит всех (interview by T. Kiryazov with Marina and Vladimir Devyatovih);

Женя, как глава дома, пожалуйста, ознакомьте со всеми собравшимися (interview by T. Kiryazov with Evgeniy Pronin and Ekaterina Kuztsenova);

Владимир Петрович, Вам как главе клана Пресняковых провести переключку... (interview by T. Kiryazov with Persnyakovih);

Когда-то в детстве была такая фраза „Большой без гармошки“. Эта такая древняя-ка... Вырос, но

Сергей, доброе утро! (interview by T. Kiryazov with Sergey); Ира, доброе утро! (interview by T. Kiryazov with Irina Rossius).

In the Russian corpus, although in extremely rare situations, one can point to examples in which the establishment of initial contact in the interview is carried out by the interlocutor, who greets the presenter with a greeting and an address or with an emotional statement:

-Здрасьте, Тимур Борисович. Спасибо, что приехали к нам -Вам спасибо, что приняли. Пожалуйста, переключку (interview by T. Kiryazov with Andrei Kaprin);

- Рады, что вы у нас в гостях!

-Спасибо! Я ведь не случайно сказал, что слова народные...Для того чтобы выбрать для себя такой путь и такой жанр, наверное, нужно иметь соответствующее происхождение Как раньше спрашивали: Вы из каких будете“ (interview by T. Kiryazov with Irina and Mihail Drovkovy).

A common pattern for establishing speech contact in video interviewing is the direct initiation of communication without the use of phatic units. This pattern is more common in the Bulgarian corpus - 48% of the interviews studied start precisely without the obligatory label elements. And in the Russian corpus they are less - 39 % of the interviews start directly:

Bulgarian language

От всичко любопитно, което можем да разкажем за Вас, нека да започнем от там, че Вие сте първата българка, която гримира действаща първа дама. Как дойде поканата да гримирате Джил Байдън? (interview by P. Dikova with Paulina Doucheva);

Мика Стоичкова срещу мен. Много се радвам, че ще направим това интервю, което планираме толкова дълго. Как си? В какъв период те намираме? (interview by P. Dikova with Mika Stoichkova);

Помислих, че фейсбук греша: Диян Неделчев на 60. Как се чувстваш? -Като едно голямо не пораснало дете (interview by P. Dikova with Diyan Nedelchev);

Златна топка, златна обувка, безброй купи и медали, бронз на Световното и всичко събрано в златата на славата, биография в 75 хиляден тираж, прекрасна съпруга, 2 дъщери и една внучка. Какво си мислите като гледате назад? (interview by P. Dikova with Hristo Stoichkov);

Ние се намираме в сватбен салон, където след по-малко от час двама души ще си обещаят да се заминават заедно, но ти си професионалист. С каква

ума не прибавилось. А здесь большой с гармошкой (interview by T. Kiryazov with Valerii Semin);

Начать хочется конечно с того, что просится, что у человека, который купил себе дом почти вырыл пруд в подмосковье, но достаточно сказать, что Сергей Куприк нас принимает (interview by T. Kiryazov with Sergey Kuprik);

В 94-ом году мы собирались. Последнее время редко видимся. Переключку проводи (interview by T. Kiryazov with Lazarevich and Nemolyaevich);

Сегодня по поводу и по случаю прихода всех наших „пока все дома“ всех своих „пока все дома“ собрал Борис, с которыми сейчас познакомит, разрезает торт, тоже авторский кстати этой семьи (interview by T. Kiryazov with Boris Krus);

За это время прибавление произошло в вашей семье. То есть Вы время зря не теряли (interview by T. Kiryazov with Anastasia Nemolyaeva and Veniamin Skalnik);

Мы уже наверное в третий раз...Вы трижды героиней нашей программы (interview by T. Kiryazov with Andrei Derzhavin);

Это уже третья наша встреча, значит Вы уже трижды героиней нашей программы (interview by T. Kiryazov with Mark Rozovskii).

Unlike the Russian corpus, the Bulgarian one contains interviews in which direct communication begins with a question. They occur in 16% of the surveyed examples:

Bulgarian language:

На ти или на Вие? – На ти разбира си, как може на Вие! С теб се познаваме от колко години...ти беше първата, която ми направи едно от първите чудесни интервюта (interview by P. Dikova with Silvena Row);

Как се чувствате когато зад Вас са 9 г. усилня? (interview by P. Dikova with the Angelovi brothers);

Какво ще кажеш за нашия стол? Добре дошла! Първи гост на него! (interview by P. Dikova with Maria Silvester);

Какво дете е Валентин-Александър? (interview by P. Dikova with Lyubka Ivancheva);

Е, как да те представя? На ти или на Вие? Как да те представя? Секс символ – дразни те. Актьор не е достатъчно, режисьор – сухо е за човек като теб. Как да те представя? (interview by P. Dikova with Asen Blatechki).

емоция дойде на работа днес? (interview by P. Dikova with Maria Chakurdukova);

Стотици хиляди фенове на сериала „Опасно изкушение“ чакат това интервю. Те Ви познават и Ви харесват. Не сте идвали в нашата красива страна. Какво бихте искали да кажете на всички, които ни гледат? (interview by P. Dikova with Sheval Sam);

Наричате себе си професионален състезател по подмладяване. Успявате да забавите скоростта на стареене с 25 %. Това надмина ли очакванията Ви? (interview by P. Dikova with Brian Johnson);

Големият победител в „Сървайвър“! Честито! И най-коментиранията знаменитост – за това не знам дали „честито“ (interview by P. Dikova with Blagoy Georgiev);

Много искахме в Коледната сутрин да се събудим в компанията на обичано и дълголетно семейство. Благодаря Ви, Силвия и Васил, че приехте нашата покана! Добре дошли и честита Коледа! (interview by P. Dikova with Silviya Lulcheva and Vasil Binev);

Ние сме от Вашите почитатели, които без „За много години“ и без песните за Коледа не може да започне празничния новогодишен сезон. Така че, благодарим Ви, че сте официалният вносител на празничното настроение в тези дни от годината и добре дошли! Благодарим, че приехте нашата покана (interview by P. Dikova with Vasil Naydenov).

Significant differences in the study of interviews in the two languages were also observed in the use of phatic emotives. There are no interviews in the Russian corpus in which communication begins with phatic emotives. And when the initial speech contact is established in the interviews from the Bulgarian corpus, the use of phatic emotives is observed in 29% of the examples. The most common pattern is address + phatic emotive to express gratitude:

Bulgarian language:

Господин Маричков, благодарим за приетата покана. Ние се вълнуваме, че сме в музикалния театър, а какво е вълнението за Вас? (interview by P. Dikova with Kiril Marichkov);

Госпожо Петкова, благодарим, че приехте нашата тематична покана – Аз благодаря, че поканихте точно мен (interview by P. Dikova with Margarita Petkova);

Господин Христов, благодарим за честта! Честит рожден ден! (interview by P. Dikova with Georgi Hristov);

Господин Куркински, много благодарим за приетата покана. Ако не се лъжа, година и половина е минала от последното Ви интервю и за нас това

значи много. Как се чувствате тук? (interview by P. Dikova with Marius Kurkinski);

Госпожо Филипова, благодаря, че приехте нашата покана – Зоравеите! (interview by P. Dikova with Ani Filipova);

Госпожо Конакчиева, много дълго чакам нашата среща и си признавам, че се вълнувам. Благодаря, че приехте нашата покана за интервю (interview by P. Dikova with Maria Konakchieva);

Господин Шенкер, благодаря Ви за времето, което ни отделяте! Радвам се да Ви видим. Как сте? (interview by P. Dikova with Rudolf Shenker);

Много благодаря, че си тук! Прекрасно изглеждаш! Много си красива! (interview by P. Dikova with Maria Ilieva).

Another common pattern is address + a phatic emotive to express admiration or pay a compliment:

Bulgarian language:

Уважаема принцеса Теодора фон Ауершперг, за мен е удоволствие да се запознаем! (interview by P. Dikova with Teodora von Auersperg);

Изглеждате превъзходно! Как краката ни да изглеждат по най-добрия начин? (interview by P. Dikova with Lera Brena).

In conclusion, we can draw the following conclusion: the preferred model for establishing speech contact in the interviews from the Russian corpus is the use of a phatic unit containing address + greeting (48%), while in the Bulgarian corpus the interaction is most often initiated directly. Despite the fact that the category of address in Bulgarian has a much broader morpho-syntactic potential, compared to Russian, in Bulgarian speech practice we can actually observe its less frequent use in the dialogic forms of fiction texts [9]. This statement turns out to be fully relevant for the dialogical forms of Bulgarian media discourse, where less frequent use of forms of address to the interlocutor is observed.

In contrast to the Russian corpus, in the Bulgarian corpus a rather common tendency can be outlined - the use of phatic emotives to establish initial contact with the interlocutor occurs in 29% of the interviews studied. However, a parenthesis should be opened: one should not ignore the fact that there are differences in the way men and women use phatic emotives. Women often use such expressions more than men. This is due to different social roles and gender expectations. Women are often more empathetic and supportive in communication, while men may be more likely to use a direct and information-oriented style of communication. For this reason, this paper does not claim to be comprehensive or exhaustive on the issue, but can only set the stage for future research perspectives.

Greeting the interlocutor is the least frequently used phatic unit for establishing initial contact in interviews from both corpora.

Russian language	Bulgarian language
1. Address with a greeting – 48 %	1. Direct start of the interaction – 48 %
2. Direct start of the interaction – 39 %	2. Phatic emotives – 29%
3. Greeting – 13 %	3. Greeting – 19 %

The use of phatic units to establish initial speech contact with the interlocutor is, on the one hand, a marker of the journalist's demonstration of good social and communicative skills and, on the other hand, sets the tone for a comfortable atmosphere in the structure of the dialogic interaction and builds positive bonds of trust between the participants in the video interview.

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